

Transformation of Sucrose : Synthesis of 1',6,6'-triamino-1',6,6'-trideoxy and 1',2,6,6'-tetramino-1',2,6,6'-tetradeoxy Sucroses

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Mesylation of sucrose with 3 and 4 moles of methane sulfonyl (Mesyl) chloride separately followed by acetylation in pyridine on chromatographic separation gave tri-O-mesyl tetra-O-mesyl and penta-O-mesyl sucrose acetates. Tri- and tetra-O-mesyl sucrose acetates are converted into their amino derivatives via azido compounds.

PREPARATION of tri-O-tosyl sucrose was first reported by Hockett and Zief¹. Since then various research groups²⁻⁶ have reported on the tosyl esters of sucrose and their conversion into polyfunctional derivatives. However, progress on the subject has not been satisfactory. The structure of tri-O-tosyl sucrose proposed by previous workers^{2,7} arrived at by different methods was strongly criticized by later investigators^{8,11,12}. In their attempts to prepare tri-O-tosyl sucrose Ball and coworkers⁸ observed the formation of about a dozen different products but could separate only two isomers of tri-O-tosyl sucrose and that too in very poor yields and lacking in crystallinity. Apart from the tosyl chloride, some work on the bulky sulfonylating agents has also been recently reported^{9,10} but no team of workers has studied the sulfonylation of sucrose by less bulky sulfonylating agents.

We have, therefore, undertaken the preparation of mesyl esters of sucrose, for the study of reactivities of different hydroxyl groups in sucrose, and their conversion into amino derivatives via azido compounds. In the present work we have extended our studies to tri- and tetra-O-mesyl sucrose acetates.

As is well known, amino sugars are components of antibiotics and antibacterial polysaccharides. An interest was, therefore, shown in the synthesis of amino derivatives of sucrose. Various authors^{11,14} have reported the preparation of mono-, di- and tri-amino derivatives of sucrose from tosyl esters, but the preparation of tetraamino derivatives of sucrose has not been reported so far from any of the sulfonic esters of sucrose. The present communication reports the preparation of 1', 6, 6'-triamino-1', 6, 6'-trideoxy- and 1', 2, 6, 6'-tetra-amino-1', 2, 6, 6'-tetradeoxy sucroses from the corresponding mesyl esters of sucrose.

Experimental

General : All evaporations were carried out under reduced pressure below 50°. Melting points were recorded in capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Optical rotations were measured on a

Bellingham Stanley type-I polarimeter in 1 dm tubes. Column chromatography on silica gel was carried out at room temperature using BDH India (60-120 mesh) silica gel activated at 120° before use. Thin layer chromatography was performed at room temperature on silica gel G BDH India containing 13% CaSO₄ as binder. The spraying reagent used was 10% solution of conc. H₂SO₄ in ethanol. NMR spectra were recorded in chloroform-d on FTXL-100 instrument except compound (8) which has been recorded on varian 60 instrument with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. All the solvents used were BDH India, dried and freshly distilled before use. R_f values were recorded by using 0.25 mm silica gel coated plates.

Trimolar mesylation of sucrose followed by acetylation : Three equivalents of mesyl chloride (3.75 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of sucrose (5 g) and pyridine (100 ml) at 0° over 15 to 20 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hrs at 0° and subsequently kept at room temperature for 24 hrs. Acetic anhydride (20 ml) was dropwise added to the same reaction mixture at room temperature and was left for 24 hrs. The reaction product was poured onto iced-water with stirring. The powdery product was filtered off dried and dissolved in acetone. The solution was decolourized with activated animal charcoal filtered and poured with stirring onto iced-water. The resulting white amorphous powder (9 g) showed on tlc (chloroform : acetone, 4 : 1) a fast moving fraction (sucrose octa-acetate) and three conspicuous slow moving products with some other minor impurities.

The powdery substance (8 g) on elution over silica gel (300 g) with chloroform : acetone, 6 : 1 gave three products :

(1) (1.6 g, 14%), R_f value 0.36 (chloroform : acetone, 4 : 1), m.p. 72-73°. [α]_D²⁰ +46.7° (c 1.2, chloroform). IR : ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1175 cm⁻¹, 1362 cm⁻¹ (-O-SO₂); 1750 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O). NMR data

(CDCl₂): γ 4.28 (d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1); 4.42-4.74 (m, 3 protons H-3, 3' and 4'); 4.91 (t, 1 proton, $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4); 5.06 (q, 1 proton $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2); 6.7-7.0 (s, 9 protons, 3Ms Superimposed); 7.62-8.12 (m, 15 protons, 5Ac). Due to overlapping, other resonances could not be interpreted. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₃₈O₁₀S₅: C, 38.1; H, 4.83; S, 12.2. Found: C, 37.9; H, 4.8; S, 11.8.

These data indicate that this compound is 1', 6, 6'-tri-O-mesyl sucrose penta-acetate (1).

(2) (1.4 g, 11.7%), R_f value 0.26 (chloroform: acetone, 5:1), m.p. 76-77°. $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 47^\circ$ (c 1.1, chloroform). IR: ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1175 cm⁻¹, 1360 cm⁻¹ (-O-SO₂-); 1750 cm⁻¹ (ester). NMR data (CDCl₂): γ 4.26 (d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1); 4.4-4.74 (m, 3 protons, H-3, 3' and 4'); 4.9 (t, 1 proton, $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4); 5.28 (q, 1 proton, $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2); 6.7-7.1 (s, 12 protons, 4 Ms Superimposed); 7.7-8.1 (m, 12 protons, 4 Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted due to overlapping. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₄H₃₈O₁₀S₄: C, 35.0; H, 4.6; S, 15.6. Found: C, 34.7; H, 4.4; S, 15.2.

These data indicate that this compound is 1', 2, 6, 6'-tetra-O-mesyl sucrose tetra-acetate (2).

(3) (0.8 g, 6.4%). R_f value 0.18 (chloroform: acetone, 5:1), m.p. 92-94°. $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 48^\circ$ (c 0.7, acetone). IR: ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1175 cm⁻¹, 1360 cm⁻¹ (-O-SO₂-), 1755 cm⁻¹ (ester). NMR data (CDCl₂): γ 4.17 (d, 1 proton, $J_{1,2}$ 3.5 Hz, H-1); 5.18 (t, 1 proton, $J_{4,5}$ 9.0 Hz, H-4); 5.28 (q, 1 proton, $J_{2,3}$ 10.0 Hz, H-2); 6.72-7.0 (s, 15 protons, 5 Ms superimposed); 7.7-8.0 (m, 9 protons, 3 Ac). The remaining resonances could not be interpreted, due to overlapping. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₃₈O₁₀S₃: C, 32.1; H, 4.4; S, 18.6. Found: C, 31.8; H, 4.2; S, 18.2.

These data indicate that this compound is 1', 2, 4, 6, 6'-penta-O-mesyl sucrose triacetate.

Tetramolar mesylation of sucrose followed by acetylation: Four equivalents of mesyl chloride (5 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of sucrose (5 g) and pyridine (100 ml) at 0° over 15-20 minutes. The reaction mixture was worked up in usual manner. White amorphous powder (9.6 g) showed on tlc (chloroform: acetone, 4:1) a fast moving fraction (sucrose octa-acetate) and three conspicuous slow moving products, as in the case of the trimolar mesylation of sucrose followed by acetylation, in 8.8%, 27% and 10.2% yields respectively.

The three compounds separated in this case were found to be 1, 2 and 3 on the basis of their mixed melting points, co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra with the respective compounds (1), (2) and (3) obtained in the case of trimolar mesylation of sucrose followed by acetylation.

(4) 3,6:1',4':3',6'-trianhydrosucrose: A solution of 1 (1 g) in methanolic sodium methoxide (1M, 40 ml) was refluxed for 3 hrs. TLC (chloroform: methanol, 8:1) showed a major component. The reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness and the residue was shaken with pyridine (5 ml) for 10-15 minutes. After the mixture was cooled to 0°, acetic anhydride (4 ml) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and then water was added to decompose the excess acetic anhydride and dissolved salts and the solution was evaporated. The residue was extracted with chloroform and dried by keeping over anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to give a crystalline residue. Recrystallization from ethanol gave 2,4-di-o-acetyl-3,6:1',4':3',6'-trianhydrosucrose (0.36 g, 76%), m.p. 180-182°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 128.4^\circ$ (c 2.1, chloroform). Lit. 8 m.p. 180-183° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 129^\circ$ (c 2.0, chloroform).

A solution of 2,4-di-o-acetyl-3,6:1',4':3',6'-trianhydrosucrose (0.3 g) in dry methanol (40 ml) was treated with catalytic amount of sodium methoxide. On leaving reaction mixture at room temperature for two days the product crystallized to give 4 (0.196 g, 85%), m.p. 190-192°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 103^\circ$ (c 1.3, water). Lit.⁸ m.p. 190.5-191.5°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 104^\circ$ (c 1.0, water).

(5) 1',6,6'-triazido-1',6,6'-trideoxysucrose penta-acetate: A mixture of 1 (1 g) and sodium azide (0.8 g) in DMF (30 ml) was heated at 120° for 48 hrs under agitation. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with acetic anhydride in pyridine to acetylate the deacetylated hydroxyl groups to a product which on purification by column chromatography on silica gel (50 g) with carbon tetrachloride: acetone, 5:1, gave a syrupy product 5 (0.56 g, 70%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 100^\circ$ (c 87, chloroform). Lit. 1⁸ $[\alpha]_D + 101^\circ$ (c 0.57, chloroform). IR: ν_{\max}^{film} 1755 cm⁻¹ (ester); 2100 cm⁻¹ (azide). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₉O₁₀N₃: C, 42.1; H, 4.6; N, 20.09. Found: C, 41.9; H 4.5; N, 19.7.

(6) 1',6,6'-triazido-1',6,6'-trideoxysucrose: A solution of 5 (0.6 g) in dry methanol (40 ml) was treated with catalytic amount of 2 M methanolic sodium methoxide at room temperature for 5 hrs with continuous stirring. The purity of the compound was checked by tlc (chloroform: ethanol, 5:3). After neutralization with Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺) (freshly regenerated and washed with methanol before use), the solution was concentrated to a syrup. The syrupy residue was boiled with light petroleum which was then decanted carefully, and this operation was repeated three to four times for complete removal of methyl acetate. The product was dried over phosphoric oxide and paraffin wax overnight to give the triazide as a syrup (6, 0.28 g, 85%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 62.9^\circ$ (c 0.8, acetone). Lit. 1⁸ $[\alpha]_D + 64^\circ$ (c 0.58, acetone).

Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{19}O_8N_3$: C, 34.5; H, 4.5; N, 30.2. Found: C, 34.3; H, 4.2; N, 29.8.

IR: ν_{\max}^{film} 2100 cm^{-1} (azide); 3460 cm^{-1} (OH).

(7) *1', 6, 6'-triamino-1', 6, 6'-trideoxysucrose*: 6 (0.2 g) was hydrogenated with platinum oxide (60 mg) as catalyst in 50% aqueous ethanol (50 ml) at 3.4 Kg/cm² of hydrogen atmosphere at 40° for 30 hrs. After the catalyst was removed the solution was concentrated to syrup. The syrup was triturated with acetone to give (7, 0.11 g, 70%, m.p. 122-124° [α]_D²⁰ + 67.7° (c 1.02, water); Lit.¹⁸ m.p. 121-125° [α]_D + 68.5° (c 0.85, water). IR: ν_{\max}^{KBr} 3100-3500 cm^{-1} (OH, NH₂); 1630 cm^{-1} . Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{25}O_7N_3$: C, 42.4; H, 7.3; N, 12.3. Found: C, 42.1; H, 7.1; N, 11.9.

(8) *1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraazide-1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraideoxysucrose tetra-acetate*: A mixture of 2 (1 g) and sodium azide (1 g) in DMF (35 ml) was heated at 125° for 60 hrs under agitation. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The residue was acetylated with acetic anhydride in pyridine in usual manner to a product which on purification by column chromatography on silica gel (50 g) with carbon tetrachloride: acetone, 5:1 gave a syrupy product (8, 0.5 g, 68%), [α]_D²⁰ + 57° (c 1.34, chloroform). IR: ν_{\max}^{film} 1760 cm^{-1} (ester); 2100 cm^{-1} (azide). NMR data (CDCl₃): γ 4.5 (d, 1 proton, J_{1,2} 2.0 Hz, H-1), 4.6-5.2 (m, 4 protons, H-3, 3', 4' and 4); 5.4-6.1 (m, 3 protons, H-5, 5' and 2); 6.15-6.8 (m, 6 protons, methylene); 7.85 (s, 12 protons, 4 Ac).

(9) *1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraazido-1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraideoxysucrose*: A sample of 8 (0.4 g) was deacetylated with 2 M methanolic sodium methoxide as described in the synthesis of 6. It gave the tetra-azide as a syrup (9, 0.24 g, 88%), [α]_D²⁰ + 45.4° (c 1.08, methanol). IR: ν_{\max}^{film} 2100 cm^{-1} (azide); 3450 cm^{-1} (OH). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{15}O_7N_4$: C, 32.5; H, 4.0; N, 38.0. Found: C, 32.3; H, 3.8; N, 37.6.

(10) *1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraamino-1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraideoxysucrose*: 9 (0.2 g) was hydrogenated with platinum oxide as described in the synthesis of compound (7). After removing the catalyst the solution was decolorized with activated animal charcoal and concentrated to a syrup. The syrup on trituration with acetone gave (10, 0.1 g, 70%) m.p. 112-115°, [α]_D²⁰ + 49.2° (c 0.9, water). IR: ν_{\max}^{KBr} 3100-3500 cm^{-1} (OH, NH₂), 1635 cm^{-1} . Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{25}O_7N_4$: C, 42.6; H, 7.6; N, 16.5. Found: C, 42.4; H, 7.3; N, 16.2.

Discussion

Mesylation of sucrose (1 mole) with mesyl chloride (3 and 4 moles) separately in pyridine at 0°

followed by acetylation with acetic anhydride in the same solution at room temperature gave a product which on chromatographic separation yielded tri-O-mesylysucrose penta-acetate(1), tetra-O-mesyl sucrose tetra-acetate(2) and penta-O-mesyl sucrose tri-acetate(3). Products (1), (2) and (3) were 1',6,6'-tri-O-mesyl-, 1',2,6,6'-tetra-O-mesyl- and 1',2,4,6,6'-penta-O-mesyl sucrose acetates respectively as confirmed by their nmr spectra. On comparing the nmr spectrum of compound (1) with that of sucrose octa-acetate, the signals due to other protons (H-2, 3,4,3' and 4') were found at their respective positions. This indicated that all the five secondary hydroxyl groups were having acetyl groups and the primary hydroxyl groups C-6, C-6' and C-1', have been mesylated. The structure of compound (1) was further confirmed by converting it into 3, 6: 1', 4': 3', 6'-trianhydrosucrose(4) in high yield, with physical constants same as reported in literature⁸. In comparison with the nmr data for octa-O-acetylsucrose, the signals due to H-2 in compound (2) and the signals due to H-2 and H-4 in compound (3) appeared at slightly higher fields i.e., at γ 5.28 and γ 5.28 and γ 5.18, respectively indicated the presence of mesyl group at C-2 in compound (2) and at C-2 and C-4 in compounds (3) respectively.

The formation of products (1), (2) and (3) clearly showed that the reactivity of different hydroxyl groups in sucrose is as follows:

Fig. 1.

- (1) $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMs$; $R^5=R^6=OAc$
 (2) $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMs$; $R^6=OAc$
 (3) $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=R^5=OMs$
 (4) $R^1=R^2=R^3=N_3$; $R^4=R^5=OAc$

Fig. 2.

- (8) $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=N_3$; $R^6=OAc$

Fig. 3.

(4) R=H

Fig. 4.

(6) $R^1=R^2=R^3=N_2$
 (7) $R^1=R^2=R^3=NH_2$

Fig. 5.

(9) $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=N_2$
 (10) $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=NH_2$

Compounds (1) and (2) on treatment with sodium azide in *N,N*-dimethylformamide gave 1', 6, 6'-triazido-1', 6, 6'-trideoxysucrose pentaacetate (5) and 1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraazido-1', 2, 6, 6'-tetra-deoxysucrose tetra acetate(8) respectively. In the

nmr spectrum of compound (8) the small value of $J_{1,2}$ (2.0 Hz) due to equatorial H-2 and equatorial H-1 coupling showed that the inversion of configuration occurred at C-2.

Compounds (5) and (8) on deacetylation with 2*M* sodium methoxide in absolute methanol gave 1', 6, 6'-triazido-1', 6, 6'-trideoxysucrose(6) and 1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraazido-1', 2, 6, 6'-tetra-deoxysucrose(9) respectively.

Compounds (6) and (9) on catalytic hydrogenation in presence of platinum oxide under 3.4 Kg/cm² hydrogen atmosphere at 40° for 25 hrs gave 1', 6, 6'-triamino-1', 6, 6'-trideoxysucrose(7) and 1', 2, 6, 6'-tetraamino- 1', 2, 6, 6'-tetra-deoxysucrose(10) respectively.

References

1. R. C. HOCKETT and M. ZIEF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1839.
2. P. D. BRAGG and J. K. N. JONES, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1959, **37**, 575.
3. R. U. LEMIEUX and J. P. BARRETTE, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1959, **37**, 1964.
4. R. KHAN, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1972, **22**, 441.
5. R. NEUMAN and J. A. IBARA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1972, **314**, 365.
6. C. H. BOLTON, L. HOUGH and R. KHAN, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1972, **21**, 138.
7. R. U. LEMIEUX and J. P. BARRETTE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2243.
8. D. H. BALL, F. H. DISSETT and R. C. CHALK, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1972, **25**, 149.
9. L. HOUGH, S. P. PHADNIS and E. TARELLI, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1975, **44**, C12.
10. R. C. ALMQUIST and E. J. REIST, *J. Carbohydr., Nucleosides Nucleotides*, 1976, **3**, 261.
11. S. UMEZAWA, T. TSUCHIYA, S. NAKADA and K. TATSUTA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1967, **40**, 395.
12. I. JEZO, *Chem. Zvesti.*, 1971, **25**, 364.
13. R. KHAN, K. S. MUPTI and M. R. JENNER, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1973, **30**, 183.
14. T. SUAMI, T. IKEDA, S. NISHIYAMA and R. ADACHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1975, **48**, 1953.
15. N. W. ISAACS, C. H. L. KENNARD, G. W. O. DONNELL and G. N. RICHARDS, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 300.
16. N. W. ISSACS and C. H. L. KENNARD, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin II*, 1972, 582.